

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ
ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ, ФАН ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ВАЗИРЛИГИ
ТОШКЕНТ МОЛИЯ ИНСТИТУТИ

“ТУРИЗМ СОҲАСИГА САЙЁҲЛАРНИ ЖАЛБ ҚИЛИШДА МИЛЛИЙ
ҲУНАРМАНДЧИЛИК МАҲСУЛОТЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ
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25 МАРТ 2023 ЙИЛ
ТОШКЕНТ
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ва маркетинг” кафедрасининг барча профессор-ўқитувчилари.

Ушбу илмий маъруза тезислари тўпламида ижтимоий-иқтисодий барқарорликни таъминлашда туризм соҳасига сайёҳларни жалб қилишда миллий ҳунармандчилик маҳсулотларини ривожлантириш истиқболлари бўйича аниқ ечимлар, шунингдек мамлакатимиз ҳамда хорижий йирик иқтисодчи олимлар, тажрибали амалиётчилар, олий ўқув юртларининг профессор-ўқитувчилари, илмий тадқиқот институтлари ва марказларининг етакчи илмий ходимлари, докторант ва мустақил изланувчиларнинг илмий тадқиқот иши натижалари мужассамлашган.

Ушбу нашрда келтирилган барча маълумотлар ва фикр-мулоҳазалар муаллифларга тегишли бўлиб, таҳрир ҳайъати аъзоларининг фикрига мос келмаслиги мумкин. Нашрда келтирилган рақамлар, статистик маълумотлар, фикр-мулоҳазалар учун муаллифлар масъул ҳисобланади.

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Continuous learning, monitoring, and adaptation are also key to success in digital marketing for craftsmanship. The digital landscape is constantly evolving, and craftsmen need to stay updated with the latest trends, technologies, and customer preferences to effectively leverage digital marketing for their crafts.

Overall, digital marketing can be a powerful tool for craftsmen to promote their crafts, connect with customers, and thrive in the digital era while maintaining the authenticity and uniqueness of their craftsmanship. By implementing digital marketing strategies thoughtfully and strategically, craftsmen can achieve their marketing objectives and succeed in the competitive digital landscape while preserving the craftsmanship heritage.

Section No. 2.

DIRECTIONS OF CREDITING OF BUSINESS ENTITIES IN THE FIELD OF HOSPITALITY

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The rapid development of the tourism services sector has mediated the formation of a powerful tourist infrastructure: regular transcontinental tourist routes are functioning, transnational hotel chains and consortia have been formed, and also initiated the need for appropriate marketing research aimed at detailing consumer preferences in the analyzed area. In accordance with the optimistic forecast of the development of world tourism, national and regional programs for the development of tourist services were formed, providing for the expansion of hotel chains, tourist transport, leisure infrastructure and catering outlets to fully meet customer demand.

Based on the above, as long as there is a demand for products and services of commercial banks in a market economy, they will function. The development or modernization of new banking products and services as the main direction of the strategic development of commercial banks is an urgent task on which the management of banks should focus their attention. The topic of the study can be considered relevant due to the growing interest of the subjects of the tourist market in bank financing caused by changes in the economic situation in the country.

Currently, UNWTO experts predict that world tourism will be able to return to pre-pandemic indicators no earlier than in 2-3 years. This is without taking into account the political risks and sanctions restrictions of recent times. Most experts pin their hopes on the revival of international tourist flows with the effect of deferred demand and an increase in vaccination rates in a number of countries. The pandemic has reduced the direct GDP from international tourism by more than 2 times: by 2 trillion US dollars, to 1.8% of world GDP. In a record 2019, the contribution of tourism to the global economy amounted to 3.5 trillion US dollars or 4% of global GDP. The political events of February-March 2022 intensified the crisis in the international tourism market.

If we evaluate the current state of the tourism market of Uzbekistan, it can be characterized both on the positive side due to the growing quantitative and qualitative indicators, and on the negative side - due to the presence of infrastructure, financial, regulatory and legal problems.

The data provided by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan confirm that the growth trend of domestic tourism will continue throughout 2022 and increased 2.8 times compared to the previous year and reached 5 million 200 thousand people. The number of tourists who arrived in the country last year increased by 3 million 400 thousand compared to the previous year. Most tourists came to the country from Kazakhstan – 1 million 551 thousand 100 people. Kazakhstan is followed by Tajikistan with 1 million 447 thousand 800, Kyrgyzstan with 1 million 356 thousand 900, Russia with 567 thousand 700, Turkey with 75 thousand and South Korea with 19 thousand 900 people.

Taking into account the results of the analysis of the above indicators, we can highlight some problems of the tourism industry — it is still the lack or satisfactory condition of infrastructure in traditional tourist and recreational areas, the low level of qualification of industry personnel, the imperfection of the regulatory framework for regulating relations between market entities, the high need for investment resources, etc.

A credit institution is an integral part of the infrastructure block of the tourist market, its interaction with market enterprises and consumers of services is ensured through investment, settlement and credit operations.

The list of subjects of the tourist market, whose activities are directly related to the provision of tourist services, includes: hotel companies, travel agents, catering companies, companies providing services for sightseeing and technical support, etc. The consumer of tourist services as a subject of the tourist market creates conditions for the development of the market due to the formation of needs. At a certain stage, the subjects face the problem of a shortage of financial resources, which can be solved by bank lending.

Among the enterprises conducting their work on the organization of recreation and entertainment, culture and sports, there is a significant proportion of entities that, in accordance with current legislation, belong to the category of microenterprises. Taking into account the positive dynamics of domestic tourism indicators and experts' forecasts for further growth, it can be assumed that the

market capacity of bank credit products designed for the purchase of tourist services will only increase and, accordingly, both credit organizations and tour operators/travel agents need to intensify cooperation.

The conducted research allowed us to draw the following conclusions.

Bank lending to tourism industry entities is of great importance for the activation of demand from consumers of tourist products, as well as for the development of domestic and inbound tourism enterprises.

- The need to change existing approaches to the organization of bank lending to tourism market entities is justified by increased competition between banks in the consumer lending segment, the need for tourism enterprises in resources, the rise in the cost of tourist products and its components.

- The transformation of a number of bank lending conditions for the subjects of the tourist market is economically feasible against the background of the growing dynamics of the indicators of the tourist services market.

- Increasing the availability of loans for consumers of tourist products in the direction of domestic tourism will ensure the growth of indicators such as the amount of income of travel agents, the number of persons placed in collective accommodation facilities, etc.

- The integration of bank lending into the development and subsequent sale of travel products of tour operators /travel agents will increase the number of vouchers sold, and the bank, accordingly, will ensure an increase in interest income.

- Microenterprises of tourism have specific problems related to the inability to secure a loan at the request of the bank (lack of collateral, stable financial indicators, etc.), in connection with which it is necessary to develop various forms of public-private support based on the experience of the USA, EU countries and Japan.

As specific directions for the development of lending to the subjects of the tourist market in relation to the Republic of Uzbekistan, we consider it appropriate to offer:

- 1) credit lines for corporate clients, which include large enterprises of the tourism industry. The interest rate varies from 15-22% per annum (with the Central Bank's main rate of 14 percent), the main share of borrowed funds falls on the autumn-spring off-season periods, the repayment conditions are determined individually, taking into account credit history, reputation in the market;

- 2) POS-lending of inexpensive tourist products - up to 3 million soums, which can be offered by TOP-10 banks, including Kapitalbank, SQB, TBC bank, Anorbank. The terms may represent an alternative to a cash loan, a consumer loan for goods, the interest rate ranges from 15-30% per annum;

- 3) consumer lending and credit cards that will suit a wide range of subjects of the tourist market, since they do not require detailed conditions (description of the tour, package of services, etc.). The disadvantage should be considered a higher percentage - 30-50% per annum, the advantage is the minimum number of documents and instant access to funds.

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ИНВЕСТИЦИОН САЛОХИЯТНИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИГА ТАЪСИР ЭТУВЧИ ОМИЛЛАР

**ТМИ “Менежмент ва маркетинг”
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Аннотация.

Инновацион-инвестицион салоҳиятнинг шаклланиши ва омиллари таҳлили, бу соҳада мавжуд услубийлар тизими таҳлил этилган, мутахассислар ва иқтисодчи-олимлар қарашлари умумлаштирилган, уларнинг мунозарали жиҳатлари баён этилган ҳамда ҳозирги замон давлат инвестиция сиёсатида ҳудуд инвестицион салоҳиятини самарали бошқаришнинг аҳамияти ва вазифалари ёритилган.

Таянч иборалар: *инвестицион салоҳият, инвестицион салоҳиятни бошқариш, инвестицион фаолият, минтақавий иқтисодиёт, ҳудудда иқтисодий ўсишнинг экзоген ва эндоген омиллари, ҳудудлар инвестицион салоҳиятини тизимли бошқариш.*

Аннотация.

Инвестиционным потенциалом региона, были анализированы системы имеющихся методик в этой области, обобщены взгляды специалистов и учёных-экономистов, изложены спорные моменты их взглядов, раскрыты значение и задачи эффективного управления инвестиционным потенциалом региона в современной инвестиционной политике государства.

Ключевые слова: *инвестиционный потенциал, управление инвестиционным потенциалом, инвестиционная деятельность, региональная экономика, экзогенные и эндогенные факторы экономического роста в регионе, системное управление инвестиционным потенциалом региона.*

Инвестицион салоҳият ҳар қандай иқтисодиётни ҳаракатга келтирувчи ва унинг тараққиётини таъминловчи омил бўлиб, барча имкониятлардан оқилана

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